

Studies on Thallous Sulphosalicylate Complex

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Thallium (I) forms a 1:1 complex with sulphosalicylate ion. The composition of the complex has been found conductometrically by applying monovariation as well as Job's continued variation methods. The dissociation constant of thallous sulphosalicylate works out to be 4.13×10^{-3} at 25°. Effect of addition of sodium hydroxide to the complex has been studied conductometrically and potentiometrically.

The complex sulphosalicylates of iron¹, copper², beryllium³, aluminium⁴, uranium⁵, and manganese⁶ have been investigated by physico-chemical methods. The various chelates are supposed to be formed by the replacement of both carboxyl as well as phenolic hydrogens, the sulphonic group being always regarded as ionised. The present communication incorporates the results of our investigation on the reaction between thallium (I) and sulphosalicylate ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Freshly prepared aqueous solutions of thallous nitrate, disodium sulphosalicylate, and sodium hydroxide were used after proper standardisation in each case. The experimental temperature was kept at 25° throughout.

Composition of the Complex

The stoichiometry of the chelate was first studied by applying monovariation method using equimolecular solutions of the reactants. In the first set the strength of the two solutions was $M/30$. Thallous nitrate was kept constant (5ml) with the variation of disodium sulphosalicylate, the total volume being always kept 25 ml by addition of distilled water. A second set of solutions was prepared similarly by taking $M/40$ equimolecular solutions. The observed conductometric data, when plotted against the volume of ligand (Fig. 1), exhibited a definite break at 5 ml of the ligand, suggesting thereby the formation of a 1:1 complex between thallous and sulphosalicylate ions.

The composition of the complex was then confirmed by the application of Job's method of continued variations⁷ using three different sets of equimolecular solutions of the reactants ($M/80$, $M/80, M/100$). The deviations from the additivity rule (Δ -conductance) were calculated from the experimental conductance values. The Δ -conductance values, when plotted against the percentage of disodium sulphosalicylate (Fig. 2), yielded three curves, each having a maximum at 50% of the ligand. This is in accord

1. Foley and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195.
2. Turner and Anderson, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 912.
3. Das and Aditya, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 19.
4. Nanda and Aditya, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 77.
5. Foley and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 909.
6. Kachhawa and Bhattacharya, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1960, 29, 315.
7. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

with the earlier observation and establishes that thalious and sulphosalicylate⁻ ions combine in 1:1 ratio to form the chelate.

Disodium sulphosal. (ml).

FIG. 1

A = $M/30$ and B = $M/40$ equimol. solns. of metal and ligand.

% Disodium sulphosal.

FIG. 2

A = $M/60$, B = $M/80$, and C = $M/100$ equimol. solns.

Stability of the Complex

The dissociation constant of the complex was found out conductometrically by applying Job's method to non-equimolecular solutions of the reactants.

FIG. 3

A. $M/100$ metal + $M/25$ ligand.
 B. " " $M/40$ "
 C. " " $M/60$ "

Three sets of solutions were prepared for this purpose; the concentration of thalious nitrate was kept $M/100$ in all the three sets, whereas the strength of the ligand solution in the three cases were $M/25$, $M/40$, and $M/50$ respectively. The Job curves obtained in this case have been shown in Fig. 3. The average value of K , the dissociation constant of the complex, worked out to be 4.13×10^{-3} at 25° .

Effect of Addition of Sodium Hydroxide to the Complex Solution

In the first set various samples were prepared by mixing 5ml of $M/40$ thalious nitrate solution with 5ml of $M/40$ disodium sulphosalicylate solution in each case. The solutions were allowed to stand for a few hours for attaining equilibrium. Varying amounts of $M/40$ sodium hydroxide solution were added to all the samples, the total volume in each case being kept constant by addition of distilled water. The second and third sets of solutions were prepared in the same way, thallium to sulphosalicylate ratio in the second set being 1:2 (5ml of metal soln. + 10ml of ligand soln.), whereas in the third set the ratio was kept 1:3 (5ml of metal soln. + 15 ml of ligand soln.). Conductance and E.M.F. values were noted down as usual. The observed data were plotted against the equivalents of alkali added. It was interesting to note that both conductance (Fig. 4) as well as potentiometric (Fig. 5) curves exhibited only one significant break in all the three cases corresponding to one equivalent of alkali. Since the disodium salt of sulphosalicylic acid was used, the only proton which could be replaced as a result of chelation was the phenolic one, the sulphonic and carboxylic hydrogens being already replaced by sodium ions. The break at one equivalent of sodium hydroxide in all the three cases therefore suggests that only a 1:1 complex is formed in the system, the chelation causing the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by thalious ion.

FIG. 4.

A=1:1, B=1:2, C=1:3 mixtures of metal and ligand, titrated with $M/40$ -NaOH.

FIG. 5

A=1:1, B=1:2, and C=1:3 metal and ligand against $M/40$ -NaOH.

Structure of the Complex

On the basis of the above experimental observations the following structure can be assigned to the thalious sulphosalicylate chelate.

This structural formula finds support from the earlier work on the metallic complexes of sulphosalicylic acid.

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